

AN INTRODUCTION TO SYNTACTIC FOAMS – THREE DIMENSIONAL COMPOSITE NETWORKS

ICCM 22

What is Syntactic?

Ancient Greek: σύνταξις

“sin.tak.sis”
arranging, organising

(same roots as “syntax”)

100 μm
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EHT = 5.00 kV

Signal A = InLens

Aperture Size = 30.00 μm

WD = 4.7 mm

Signal B = SE2

H25

Acc.V Spot Magn
4.00 kV 5.9 29x

Det WD Exp
SE 17.4 1

2 mm

Acc.V Spot Magn
4.00 kV 5.9 250x

Det WD Exp
SE 17.3 1

200 μm

Acc V

Magn

Det

WDF

200 μ m

15.0 kV

300x

SE

11.3

20 μm

EHT = 10.00 kV

Signal A = SE2

Aperture Size = 30.00 μm

WD = 20.8 mm

Apply macro

Summary

Syntactic foams : Cellular Composites

Unique material properties

Questions?

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